

ISSN 2181-9505
Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9505

Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy Universiteti
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi
Imom Buxoriy xalqaro ilmiy-tadqiqot markazi
O'zbekiston falsafa jamiyati

Национальный Университет Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека
Международный научно-исследовательский центр Имам Бухари
при Кабинете Министров Республики Узбекистан
Философское общество Узбекистана

The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
Imam Bukhari International Research Center under the Cabinet of Ministers
of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Philosophical Society of Uzbekistan

FALSAFA VA HAYOT
XALQARO JURNAL

ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ
МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ

PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE
INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

2023 № 1 (20)

Jurnal bir yilda 4 marta nashr qilinadi.
Журнал выходит 4 раза в год.
The journal is published 4 times in a year.

Toshkent-2023

SIYOSAT VA JAMIYAT FALSAFASI

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich

Liberalizm mafkurasi: genezisi, shakllanish omillari.....9-19

Shadiyev Bexzod Mirsalimovich

O‘zbekistondagi nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlar faoliyatini takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....20-25

Alimatova Nargis Abduxalilovna

Raqobat mazmunining tarixiy evolyutsiyasi.....26-32

TA’LIM VA FAN FALSAFASI

Xidirov Mustafo Toyirqulovich

Abu Nasr Forobiy va Abu Ali ibn Sinoning bilish va faoliyat uyg‘unligiga oid tabiiy-ilmiiy qarashlari.....33-40

Danilova V.S., Kojevnikov N.N.

Yevroosiyo madaniy kommunikatsiyalari va markazi: ontologik va metafizik jihatlari.....41-54

TARIX FALSAFASI VA FALSAFA TARIXI

Islamov Kamol Tashkulovich

Yevropa Uyg‘onish davri mutafakkirlari qarashlarida ijtimoiy-falsafiy fikrlar rivoji.....55-62

Burkhonov Sherzodbek Muxammadbobir ugli

Martin Xaydegger ta’limotidagi “Dasein” tushunchasi talqini.....63-68

Madalimov Timur Abduvaliyevich

Qadimgi Hindistonda Astika maktabining konseptual tahlili.....69-76

DUNYO MADANIYATI VA DINIY AN’ANALAR

Sagikizi Ayajan, Kakimjanova, Margarita Kabdulaevna, Qulibek Bagdatkali Abdimanapovich

Qozog‘iston jamiyatidagi ong transformatsiya sharoitlarida diniy qadriyatlar.....77-89

Saidzoda Daler Muxibullo

Zamonaviy jamiyat rivojlanishi sharoitlarida diniy-siyosiy ekstremizm tushunchasi tadqiqi.....90-98

Karimova Sadokat Tahirovna

Millatlararo totuvlikni ta’minlashda milliy o‘zlik va g‘urur tuyg‘ularining o‘rni.....99-109

ФИЛОСОФИЯ ПОЛИТИКИ И ОБЩЕСТВА

Хакимов Назар Хакимович

Идеология либерализма: генезис, факторы формирования.....9-19

Шадиев Бехзод Мирсалимович

Теоретические основы оптимизации деятельности неправительственных организаций в Узбекистане.....20-25

Алиматова Наргис Абдухалиловна

Историческая эволюция понятия соревнований.....26-32

ФИЛОСОФИЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И НАУКИ

Хидиров Мустафо Тойиркулович

Естественно-научные воззрения Абу Наср Фараби и Абу Али ибн Сина о гармонии познания и деятельности.....33-40

Данилова В.С., Кожевников Н.Н.

Центры и коммуникации культуры евразии: онтологические и метафизические аспекты.....41-54

ФИЛОСОФИЯ ИСТОРИИ И ИСТОРИЯ ФИЛОСОФИИ

Исламов Камол Ташкулович

Развитие социально-философских мыслей в мнениях мыслителей эпохи Возрождения Европы.....55-62

Бурханов Шерзодбека Мухаммадбобир угли

Интерпретация понятия «Dasein» у Мартина Хайдеггера.....63-68

Мадалимов Тимур Абдувалиевич

Концептуальный анализ школы Астика в древней Индии.....69-76

МИРОВАЯ КУЛЬТУРА И РЕЛИГИОЗНЫЕ ТРАДИЦИИ

Сагикызы Аяжан, Какимжанова Маргарита Кабдулаевна, Кулыбек Багдаткали Абдиманопович

Религиозные ценности в условиях трансформации сознания в Казахском обществе.....77-89

Саидзода Далер Мухибулло

Исследование понятия религиозно-политического экстремизма в контексте развития современного общества.....90-98

Каримова Садокат Тахировна

Роль чувств национальной идентичности и гордости в улучшении межнациональной гармонии.....99-109

PHILOSOPHY OF POLITICS AND SOCIETY

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich

Ideology of liberalism: genesis, formation factors.....9-19

Shadiyev Behzod Mirsalimovich

Theoretical bases of the optimisation of the activities of non-governmental organizations in Uzbekistan.....20-25

Alimatova Nargis Abduxalilovna

Historical evolution of content of competition.....26-32

PHILOSOPHY OF EDUCATION AND SCIENCE

Khidirov Mustafo Toyirkulovich

The natural-scientific views of Abu Nasr Farabi and Abu Ali Ibn Sina on the harmony of cognition and activity.....33-40

Danilova V.S., Kojevnikov N.N.

Centers and communications of eurasian culture: ontological and metaphysical aspects.....41-54

PHILOSOPHY OF HISTORY AND HISTORY OF PHILOSOPHY

Islamov Kamol Tashkulovich

Development of social and philosophical thoughts in the opinions of the Renaissance Thinkers.....55-62

Burkhonov Sherzodbek Muxammadbobir o'g'li

Interpretation of the concept of "Dasein" in Martin Heidegger.....63-68

Madalimov Timur Abduvaliyevich

A conceptual analyse of the astika schools in ancient India.....69-76

WORLD CULTURE AND RELIGIOUS TRADITIONS

Sagikizi Ayajan, Kakimjanova, Margarita Kabdulayevna, Qulibek Bagdatkali Abdimanapovich

Religious values in the conditions of transformation of consciousness in the Kazakhstan society.....77-89

Saidzoda Daler Muxibullo

Study of the concept of religious-political extremism in the context of the development of modern society.....90-98

Karimova Sadokat Tahirovna

Role of national identity, pride the emotions in improving interethnic harmony.....99-109

UDC: 1:141.32

 10.5281/zenodo.10073149

Burkhonov Sherzodbek Muxammadbobir ugli
Doctoral student of the National University of Uzbekistan
E-mail: burkhanovsh95@gmail.com
(Uzbekistan, Tashkent)

INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPT OF “DASEIN” IN MARTIN HEIDEGGER

Abstract. Martin Heidegger introduces the concept of “Dasein” into his philosophy. This concept represents the meaning of human existence. According to Heidegger, it is fundamentally different from other kinds of being. The concept of “Dasein” does not represent the material existence of a person, but, on the contrary, the existence of his consciousness.

Key words: Dasein, existence, concept, existential, own, philosophical, presence.

ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ПОНЯТИЯ «DASEIN» У МАРТИНА ХАЙДЕГГЕРА

Аннотация. Мартин Хайдеггер вводит в свою философию понятие «Dasein». Это понятие отражает смысл человеческого существования. По мнению Хайдеггера, оно принципиально отличается от других видов бытия. Понятие «Dasein» представляет собой не материальное существование человека, а, наоборот, существование его сознания.

Ключевые слова: Dasein, существование, понятие, экзистенциальное, собственное, философское, присутствие.

MARTIN XAYDEGGER TA'LIMOTIDAGI “DASEIN” TUSHUNCHASI TALQINI

Annotatsiya. Martin Xaydegger o'z falsafasiga "Dasein" tushunchasini kiritadi. Bu tushuncha inson mavjudligining ma'nosini aks ettiradi. Xaydeggerning fikricha, u boshqa mavjudot turlaridan tubdan farq qiladi. "Dasein" tushunchasi insonning moddiy mavjudligini emas, aksincha uning ongining mavjudligini anglatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Dasein, mavjudlik, tushuncha, ekzistensial, shaxsiy, falsafiy, mavjudlik.

INTRODUCTION

Martin Heidegger saw his task as a philosopher in substantiating the doctrine of the essence and meaning of being in a new way. To achieve this goal, he sought to find ways to improve the adequacy of the transmission of his thoughts by means of language. His efforts are aimed at conveying the subtlest shades of meaning through the maximum use of the content of philosophical terms.

M. Heidegger seeks to identify those fundamental attitudes of European thinking that gave rise to an undesirable state of the entire European civilization. The most important of these attitudes, according to the philosopher, offered to focus on overcoming the mental culture that already has 300 years. It was she who led Europe to a dead end, and it is necessary to look for a way out of it, listening to the whisper of being.

Questions about whether humanity is going where it needs to go and whether it should go in the direction in which it is moving worried many European thinkers. Heidegger, reflecting on them, goes further and asks: "Are we not the last of some historical accomplishment, which is now rapidly coming to an end, where everything will be completed in some increasingly tedious order of uniformity".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Martin Heidegger (1889-1976) is regarded as one of the originators of German existentialism. There are two periods in the work of the thinker. The first period lasted from 1927 until the mid-1930s. The second period of creativity begins in 1935 and continues until the end of his life.

Heidegger's search for the meaning of being was initially aimed at revealing and unlocking temporality. However, the path to this last foundation of what has been asked is long and difficult, because what is at stake is the fate of metaphysics in its original sense, unclouded by history.

Let us dwell on these difficulties in more detail, using "Being and Time" as a guide to them. Heidegger himself points out the difficulties: until a translucent idea of being in general is obtained, "the renewed temporal analysis of presence will also remain incomplete and weighed down by ambiguities - not to mention various substantive difficulties" [1, p. 333].

Dasein is one of the main concepts of the great philosophical book "Sein und Zeit" by Martin Heidegger. It was translated from German by V.V. Bibikhin in the meaning of "presence" and the purpose of this book, according to the author, is "the specific development of the question of the meaning of "being" [1, 1997, p. 1], which is inextricably linked with the interpretation of time.

Moreover, "the concept of being is rather the darkest" [1, p. 3]. And if there is such an understanding, then a religious faith is hardly possible for a philosopher, and the meaning of being is not just divorced from transcendent and not only "the darkest", but also resides exclusively in time. Heidegger writes: "Both the non-temporal and the super-temporal in the aspect of their being are also temporal" [1, p. 18]. That is, there is no eternal transcendental world, but there are eternally renewing sensual and transcendental worlds. And such worlds and such being,

indeed, have “temporal certainty.” And the structures of Dasein (presence) in it will indeed be “modes of temporality” [1, p. 17].

Probably, Heidegger was led in this direction by his favorite thinker Friedrich Nietzsche, who said: “The real person is of much higher value than the “desirable” person of any of the previous ideals” [4, p. 161]. What is positive in Heidegger's chosen approach is that, building his “axioms” and his “coordinate system” (without God, the devil, demons, sin, repentance, etc.), he wants to explain and explains that most complex and concrete problematic of human Dasein, which, of course, always in time and always in everyday life, with “people”, and in the existential of care, fear, etc.

METHODS

Heidegger reveals temporality through the question of the possible integrity of the structure of Dasein. But how does Heidegger's reasoning itself lead to this question, and why does it arise?

Heidegger in his philosophy does not set the task of saving the world. His goal as a thinker is more modest, it is to understand the world in which one has to live. He writes: “Philosophy seeks what is being...”. And further: “It exists in the melody of conformity, tuned to the voice of the Being of being.”

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The immediate goal of the existential analytics of Dasein is to isolate a single initial structure of being-to-be, which determines the possibility and mode of being Dasein. Under the phenomenological scope is, first of all, the comprehension of the original being of Dasein, promulgated as concern. An analysis of the basic structure of Dasein would require an exposition of the entire philosophy of Heidegger, so we will dwell only on the main points.

The immediate goal of the existential analytics of Dasein is to isolate a single initial structure of being-to-be, which determines the possibility and mode of being Dasein [1]. Under the phenomenological scope is, first of all, the comprehension of the original being of Dasein, promulgated as concern. An analysis of the basic structure of Dasein would require an exposition of the entire philosophy of Heidegger, so we will dwell only on the main points [2].

The main attention in the philosophy of M. Heidegger is given to the analysis of the meaning of the category of being, which is filled with a kind of content. In his opinion, “Being from the early beginning of Western European thought to this day means the same as presence. From presence, presence, the present sounds. The latter, according to popular notion, forms with the past and future a characteristic of time. Being as presence is determined by time.” In other words, Heidegger's being is the existence of things in time, or existence.

According to Heidegger, human existence is the core theme of understanding everything that survives. The thinker denotes human being by the term “Dasein”, breaking with the philosophical tradition in which this term denotes “existent being”, “existing”. In Heidegger, according to the researchers of his

work, “Dasein” rather means the being of consciousness. The ancestor of German existentialism emphasizes that only a person knows about his mortality and only he knows the temporality of his existence. Because of this, he is able to realize his being [3].

Human existence is Dasein – “here-being”, finite, present existence. Its essence is existence - openness, striving for something else, access to Nothing (beyond the limits of any being, any objectivity). Striving for Nothing is an expression of our finiteness, temporality, but at the same time it is an entry into the truth of being. Being, in essence, is Being unto death.

The existence of a person in the everyday world can be characterized as “own” and “improper”. “Existence not proper” is life “according to the type of others”. In “inauthentic being” a person is completely immersed in the existent, and he does not remember his own death, because his world is impersonal.

“Own being” is associated with the awareness of one's mortality. In death, a person is not a function, not an object among objects. Here he is unique. He who has realized death exists, he is always ahead of himself.

It is known that the Heideggerian project is an attempt to lay a new beginning in ontology. Moreover, time, properly rethought when posing the question of being, acts as the ultimate ontological foundation, therefore Heidegger's ontological turn is associated primarily with the disclosure of the ontological role of time.

In the first part of our article “Heidegger’s version of the phenomenology of the temporality of human existence: the question of the integrity of Dasein” we demonstrated how the identification of temporality is connected with the question of the possible integrity of the structure of Dasein. Let us now turn to the difficulties that the phenomenological description of time gives rise to and try to answer the question: does Heidegger achieve the original dimension of temporality?

Let's start with the following thesis: “Phenomenologically, initially, temporality appears in its own whole being of presence, in the phenomenon of intervening determination” [1, p. 304]. In other words, temporality manifests itself initially in an intervening determination. M. Fleischer notes:

“The original and proper temporality have the same structure. Proper temporality appears as an existential fulfillment of the original temporality in the actual existing Dasein. The event of temporality (Zeitigungsgeschehen) of original temporality makes this performance possible, but is not identical with it. Then the original temporality as the being of Dasein must be found in every Dasein, also in the non-properly existent, and this is all the more true because Dasein, according to Heidegger, in fact “proximately and for the most part” exists non-properly. The original dimension (Ursprungsdimension) of temporality lies outside its own temporality, but which, as was said, as an existential fulfillment of original temporality, is just structurally similar to it and is “manifested” in its own care” [5, p. 19].

As the future, the advancing determination-for-itself-advance (Auf-sich-zukommen) testifies. The intervening determination is existentially “being toward its very distinctive capacity to be. This is possible only in such a way that presence in general, in its very possibility, is able to come for itself... Intercession makes Dasein properly present, namely, in such a way that intercession is itself possible, only in so far as Dasein as being in general already always occurs for itself, i.e., in general, in its being, it is advancing” [1, p. 325].

Thus, on the one hand, we have our own future as an existential fulfillment of intercession in a certain modified Dasein, and the original future as in the being of Dasein in general is always already happening - on the other hand, our own future is here founded in the original (in the same way, the original future is subject to non-proper being, as evidenced by the following: “If to the being of presence belongs proper corresponding non-proper being towards death, then it is possible only as coming in the indicated ... sense” [1, p. 325].

Further, determination as a mode of understanding “means existing to accept being-guilty, to be thrown on the basis of insignificance. But to accept abandonment means actually to be a presence in the way it has always been” [1, p. 325]. This return of Dasein to itself “as it has always been”, which means: to its own being, is the fulfillment of its own existence. How is this possible? - “Only insofar as there is a presence at all as I am-former... ” [1, p. 326]. It would seem clear: the formerness of original temporality substantiates the formerness of one's own temporality. The dimension of being and the fulfillment of existence are clearly distinguished here.

According to Augustine, it can be stated that “Only that moment in time can be called present, which cannot be divided even into the smallest parts, but it is so swiftly carried away from the future into the past! It has no duration. If it lasted, it would be possible to separate the past from the future in it; the present does not continue.” Augustine states a certain paradox: what we call time - the most “secret and ordinary” - in the form of its three possible modifications can only exist in the soul [6, p. 219] of the original temporality, while Dasein in the nearest and the most part exists non-properly, then what is non-proper temporality?

In the next part, we will try to outline possible moves to answer this question. But for the time being, one more remark of Heidegger himself: “Disclosure here and the existential possibilities of presence, property and non-property, are founded in temporality” [1, p. 350]. Should this temporality be understood as initial?

Thus, the existential possibilities of Dasein, property and non-property, are founded in temporality. That is, temporality must be subject to this differentiation, so that the fundamental structures of Dasein are comprehended as modes of temporality of temporality, but at the same time, differentiation must be “reduced” to the whole: “The temporary constitution of these phenomena always goes back to a single temporality, which as such vouches for the possible structural unity of understanding, disposition, fall and speech” [1, p. 335]. Temporality is constitutive not only for the improper and proper modalities of the existence of Dasein, but also for the existential distinction of openness, namely, as regards, first of all, understanding, disposition and being - with an intra-worldly being - temporality is fulfilled in each case in all three ecstasies:

“Understanding is based primarily on the future (intercession vs. expectation). The location of time is primary in the former (renewal, respectively, forgetfulness). The fall is primarily rooted in time in the present (actualization of the corresponding blink-of-an-eye). Nevertheless, understanding is always the "existing" present. Nevertheless, the arrangement of time is as “actualizing” the future. Nevertheless, the actuality is repelled from the past future” [1, p. 350].

For speech “there remains” no ecstasy par excellence. Therefore, in Heidegger we find six phenomena of time. As for one's own temporality, we find: understanding as an intervening determination, disposition as the choice of accepting abandonment, and, finally, the openness of the situation in the act of the actual existent Dasein. The question of the possible differentiation of one's own and original temporality here remained problematic.

With regard to improper temporality, much more problematic, and sometimes even dead ends, were discovered. So, we find: understanding (self-thrown), which temporizes itself mainly as expectation, disposition (characterized by fear), showing itself initially as self-forgetfulness, and falling (lost in people and with care), actualizing temporal. However, as has been shown, the nonproper temporality "emerges" as the present par excellence, and the present, if there must be an initial primary temporal ecstasy, turns out to be such an ecstasy.

And since the original dimension of temporality cannot be reached in an obvious way, the entire structure of degeneration is found to be devoid of a foundation.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we note that understanding the dialectic of human existence and all that exists, one way or another, leads to the problem of combining the semantic fields of ontology and anthropology [10]. The value of the ontological analysis of time in the context of the Dasein structure lies in focusing on the importance of the role of time in the understanding and cognition of being, in revealing the meaning of being a person. If we do not take into account the significance of time in the processes of the universe and even in everyday life, the meaning of being will be missed, and a person will be immersed in the abyss of inauthenticity and despair.

BIBLIOGRAPHIES

1. Heidegger M. Being and time / trans. V.V. Bibikhin. – M., 1997.
2. Rosales A. Transzendenz and Differenz. Ein Beitrag zum Problem der onto-logischen Differenz beim fruehen Heidegger. – Koeln, 1966.
3. <https://www.grandars.ru/college/filosofiya/filosofiya-haydeggera.html>
4. Nietzsche F. Will to power. The experience of reassessing all values. – M.: IChP "Zhanna", 1994.
5. Fleischer M. Die Zeitanalysen in Heideggers "Sein und Zeit": Aporien, Probleme und ein Ausblick. – Wuerzburg, 1991.
6. Augustine A. Confession / per. M.E. Sergeenko. – M., 1997.